

ENVIRONMENTAL STRESS-RUPTURE MECHANISMS

IN GLASS FIBRE/POLYESTER LAMINATES

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Summary

It has previously been shown that for certain laminates tested in seawater at elevated temperatures, stress-rupture behaviour follows different laws in the ranges of stress above and below 50% UTUL (a parameter related to the tensile strength) of the dry laminate. The paper describes a study being made to identify failure mechanisms under both regimes, and hence to establish a sound basis for obtaining design data by extrapolation from accelerated tests.

Measurements of creep strain for samples tested in air suggest that 50% UTUL may be a "creep-rupture limit" below which dry samples will not fail.

The proportion and distribution of fibre breaks in longitudinal rovings have been recorded as functions of applied load, in short-term sub-critical loading tests. 50% UTUL appears to be the threshold for "multi-filament" fractures.

In immersed tests at 60 C, conjoint action between stress and moisture produces extremely rapid debonding at crossover points in the woven reinforcement. This is considered to be more important than the increase in water uptake as a function of stress, which has also been observed.

Surface flaws, attributable to stress-corrosion, have been identified on fibres at the crossover points, near the location of final fracture in failed testpieces from immersed stress-rupture tests.

Based on these observations, a self-consistent explanation of the observed stress-rupture behaviour is presented.

Introduction.

Commencing in 1979, an extensive programme of tests has been performed in the School of Materials Science at the University of Bath, to obtain data upon the tensile stress-rupture behaviour of commercial laminates in seawater at various temperatures. The work was funded predominantly* by the Central Electricity Generating Board of the U.K. (CEGB), in support of a programme to extend the use of GRP in the cooling circuits of coastal power stations (1).

It was required, by the extrapolation of results from tests of up to two years duration, to determine design stresses leading to a thirty year life under specified conditions. Some results of this work have been published, (2,3), and in particular it was observed that for tests at elevated temperatures (40 C, 60 C), stress-rupture plots of applied stress versus (log) time to failure could not be adequately represented by the expected straight lines. Instead, as Figure 1 shows, a discontinuity or "knee" was observed at load levels around fifty percent of the short-term failure load. This has serious implications for extrapolation based on short-term tests, since it suggests that different failure mechanisms operate in the two load ranges, above and below the "knee".

A research programme was therefore established to investigate the mechanisms of environmental creep damage in polyester/glass composites, and thus to define the range of conditions under which reliable accelerated tests can be carried out. This paper presents a brief review of the work undertaken to date.

* Full acknowledgements are given at the end of the paper.

Figure 1. Mean lifetime as a function of tensile load, for polyester/glass laminates tested in seawater at three temperatures. Full lines, best fit for tests at 40 C. After Reference 3.

Materials

Except where stated, work reported here was performed upon laminates made by hand lay-up to a specification supplied by CEGB, using an isophthallic polyester resin with a mixed reinforcement comprising chopped strand mat of 0.3kg/sq.m (CS), and bidirectional woven rovings of 0.83kg/sq.m (WR) in the following sequence: [CS, WR, CS](symmetrical). The total glass loading was therefore 2.86kg/sq.m. Laminates were post-cured for five hours at 60 C.

Testpieces were machined to give a parallel sided central portion 65mm long by 25mm wide. End tabs were 38mm wide by 90mm long, and shoulder radius was 75mm. Identical testpieces were used for creep-rupture and for orthodox tensile tests at constant crosshead speed, normally 5mm per minute.

The strengths of laminates are expressed in this paper as the Ultimate Tensile Unit Load (UTUL), a quantity defined in British Standard 4994, 1973 as:

$$UTUL = \frac{\text{Breaking Load}}{\text{Sample width} \times \text{Glass loading}}$$

This parameter is preferred to Tensile Strength because it eliminates the effect of variations in sample thickness. The mean value of UTUL for laminates made for this programme was 219 N/mm. Applied loads in creep and stress-rupture tests are expressed as percentages of the appropriate mean UTUL. In Figure 1, the value is 256 N/mm.

Experimental.

Work reported here is grouped under four main headings:

(1) Creep monitoring of samples loaded in air.

The objective here is to discern features early in a test, which correlate with time to failure, thus forming the basis of a life prediction method. Thirty-millimetre long strain gauges were bonded to the samples, and an eight-channel strain monitor of high gain and stability (built "in-house") was used in conjunction with a Commodore 4032 to record strain as a function of time. Acoustic emission has been simultaneously monitored in a number of tests, using a Physical Acoustics 3400 system to record event count and peak amplitude as functions of time, on up to four testpieces at a time. Six load levels, in the range 57% to 85% UTUL have been explored.

(2) Study of damage under short-term sub-critical loading.

To isolate the effect of load alone upon the main load-bearing fibres in the mixed reinforcement, ie the longitudinal rovings, single-ply WR laminates were prepared, and samples loaded in tension to chosen sub-critical strain levels. A standard coupon was then cut from the gauge length, the resin was burned off, and samples numbering approximately two hundred fibres were extracted from several rovings, care being taken to disturb the relative positions of the fibres as little as possible.

The samples were dispersed in a solvent, and transmission optical microscopy was used to determine the number of fibre breaks per unit length of fibre. Attention was also paid to the grouping of breaks in neighbouring fibres: in particular, a multi-filament fracture is one where breaks occur side by side in two or more fibres.

(3) Interrupted immersed creep-rupture tests.

To study the development of damage under the two regimes suggested by the form of the curves in Figure 1, samples were exposed at two load levels, above and below the "knee", in distilled water at two temperatures: 20 and 60C. The higher load level, 60% UTUL, was the same at each temperature, since this was expected to produce similar lives (Fig. 1). For the lower load level, 30% UTUL was chosen in tests at 60 C, and 40% UTUL in tests at room temperature, again to achieve similar lives. For each test condition up to sixteen samples were loaded, to be successively removed for examination according to a predetermined time schedule based on the expected life. Water uptake was measured by drying out a portion of each sample. The remainder was examined for extent of debonding, growth of resin cracks and, in failed samples, fibre surface condition. For comparison, several samples were examined after exposure to water without the application of load.

(4) Study of testpieces after creep rupture.

To characterise damage in the critical region where failure ultimately occurred, fracture surfaces were examined using scanning electron microscopy: (SEM). Subsequently, longitudinal fibres in the immediate vicinity of the fracture were studied in the SEM after burning off the resin. About forty samples from the CEEB programme (2) have been studied, covering the full range of load levels, being taken mostly from the group exposed at 60 C. A smaller set from the dry creep-rupture programme has been examined for comparison.

Results and Discussion.

(1) Creep

(a) Form of creep curves. Up to approximately 85% UTUL, creep curves showed the classical three stage behaviour: a primary period of loading and transient creep, at the end of which the strain had reached the value $e(i)$, Figure 2a; a secondary stage corresponding to the "steady-state" creep of a metal, during which the strain increased in a stepwise fashion, with negligible change between steps, up to the value $e(s)$; and a tertiary stage of accelerating creep leading to failure. The third stage is not shown in Figure 2a. At higher loads, the secondary stage became vanishingly small, Figure 2b.

A corresponding variation was shown by the acoustic emission (AE) output. Stepwise increases in strain during stage 2 correlated with bursts of high-amplitude AE, see inset to Figure 2a. It should be noted that AE peaks not accompanied by strain increments in Figure 2a almost certainly arose from growth of cracks outside the 30mm gauge length.

The strain increments in stage 2 are thought to be associated with bursts of fibre failures within a single roving, producing transverse cracks whose length may equal the roving width. Such cracks have been observed, though not during formation, and it is thought to be unlikely that failures of one or two fibres could produce the observed changes in sample compliance.

Figure 2. Tensile creep curves for polyester-glass laminates tested in air at room temperature. For $e(i)$, $e(s)$, see text.

A. Creep at 57% UTUL, showing primary and stepwise secondary stages.

INSET. AE: peak amplitude recorded in sample interval, versus elapsed time. Numbers show correspondence of AE peaks with strain increments.

B. Creep at 85% UTUL, showing primary and tertiary stages only.

(b) Creep strain and sample life. Figure 3 shows how the initial strain, $e(i)$, maximum secondary strain, $e(s)$, and the creep strain, defined as

$$e(c) = e(s) - e(i)$$

vary with the applied load. Also shown, at point P, is the failure strain in a tensile test at 0.5mm/minute crosshead speed, a loading rate which approaches that used in the creep tests, approximately 0.3mm/minute. Clearly, point P lies at 100% UTUL, and the creep strain must be zero. The equivalent point for the creep tests is the intersection of curves of $e(i)$ and $e(s)$, and at the same load, $e(c)$ intersects the load axis.

The horizontal line AB shows the minimum failure strain recorded in a series of tensile tests at different crosshead speeds. This is identified as the short-term failure strain. The intersection of AB with the curve for $e(s)$ defines a load level below which, it is postulated, $e(s)$ fails to reach the lowest recorded failure strain, and, under dry conditions, creep rupture will not occur.

Figure 4 shows the relationship between time to failure, (ttf), and initial strain, $e(i)$. In view of the direct relationship between $e(i)$ and applied load, it was to be expected that ttf would increase as $e(i)$ decreased. However, Figure 4 suggests that ttf increases without limit as $e(i)$ approaches 0.8%, corresponding to about 50% UTUL, the value identified as a "creep-rupture limit" in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Analysis of observed strains in creep tests.
 $e(i)$: strain on initial loading. $e(s)$: maximum strain, stage 2.
 $e(c)$: creep strain. P and AB, see text.

Figure 4. Relationship between initial strain, $e(i)$, in creep test, and time to failure, for tests in air.

(2) Short-term fibre damage

Figure 5 shows the increasing incidence of fibre breaks in longitudinal rovings as load increases. The most significant feature is that only above 50% UTUL were multi-filament fractures observed.

Figure 5. Incidence of fibre fractures in longitudinal rovings after short-term loading of single-ply laminate. Points are the mean of eight determinations.

Figure 6. Water uptake at 60 C by polyester/ glass laminates exposed under the stated tensile loads.

(3) Load/ Environment Interactions

(a) Water uptake. Figure 6 shows that the water uptake at 60 C was increased at higher load levels. Similar results have been obtained at 20 C, although water contents and uptake rates were lower.

(b) Debonding. Debonding of WR at the crossover points could be detected by a checker-board pattern of whitened areas. It is clearly the result of conjoint action by load and environment, since none was observed in dry samples, nor in samples immersed under no load for sixty days in water at 60 C. By contrast, extensive debonding was present after eleven days under 30% UTUL in water at this temperature, Figure 7. At the higher load of 60% UTUL only seven hours was required to produce the same effect; the water content at that time being little over half that achieved in the longer test. Furthermore, the onset of debonding was greatly delayed in samples with edges sealed with silicone rubber. These observations together imply that in stressed samples, water has rapid access to the crossover points by way of cracks formed along the transverse rovings.

(c) Fibre Damage. Evidence of moisture attack upon longitudinal fibres was found during SEM fractographic examination of creep-rupture samples from the CEGB programme. Surface pitting as illustrated in Figure 8 was seen on pulled-out fibres. Subsequent examination of rovings separated from the matrix revealed similar features on fibres which had been in contact with weft rovings at crossover points away from the fracture surface. The pits are certainly a product of environmental attack, since none has been found in samples tested in air.

Figure 7. Debonding of woven rovings in laminate loaded at 30% UTUL for eleven days in water at 60 C, shown by "checker-board" pattern of dark areas. Transmitted light.

Figure 8. Pits on the surface of a glass fibre in the crossover region of two rovings. From laminate exposed to seawater at 60 C for 75 days under a load of 25% UTUL.

Creep-Rupture Mechanisms.

For the temperatures and environments of interest, it is the accepted view that the only contribution made by continuous reinforcement fibres to the creep of composites is by fracture or by straightening of crimp (4). In WR, attention is focussed upon the crossover regions, where it has been shown (5) that high and non-uniform stresses exist in rovings in the loading direction. The present investigation has further shown these regions to be preferential sites for absorbed water in stressed laminates, and, presumably as a result, preferential sites for pitting attack upon the fibres. It is to be expected, therefore, that the growth of some form of defect to critical size (causing catastrophic failure) will occur at crossover points.

The time-dependence of defect growth can arise from two causes: load transfer from the vicinity of broken fibres by creep of the resin, which will be stress- and temperature-dependent; and enlargement of fibre pits by environmental attack, which will be influenced by stress, environment and temperature, (6).

Time to failure will clearly be influenced also by the number and severity of defects present after the initial loading. The load level of 50% UTUL appears to be significant because it represents a threshold for multi-filament fractures. The observed variations in creep-rupture behaviour may be rationalised in the following way:

(a) Below 50% UTUL, single-filament fractures only are produced upon loading. In dry samples there is little driving force for multiplication of fractures, (7), and failure may never occur. In wet samples, environmental attack of the glass, concentrated at crossover points, will eventually initiate failure. Failure time is relatively insensitive to stress in this range because: (i) the number of fibre fractures varies slowly with load, and the fractures remain well separated; (ii) the contribution of stress to the activation of fibre pitting is small. Thus, chemical effects dominate, and in particular temperature, even over the narrow range studied here, exerts its influence.

(b) Above 50% UTUL, multi-filament fractures cause high local stress concentrations, encouraging spread of damage to neighbouring fibres with the formation of roving cracks. Shorter lives are attributable to the smaller "critical defect size", which is roughly proportional to the inverse square of the applied stress. Resin creep is the rate-determining factor in dry samples. Environment exerts an influence upon immersed samples through stress-induced pitting in the load range 50 to 85% UTUL, but the higher level of stress activation causes secondary effects such as water temperature to be insignificant. Above 85% UTUL, the accumulation of damage through the medium of resin creep is so rapid that environment ceases to be important.

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